

**TIME DILATION
WITH MASS
AND VELOCITY**

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Hello my name is Blaise Dmello, I am from India. The objective of my Hypothesis is to relate that if we have an object with any given mass and if we add a particular velocity to it, it will cause time to slow down in it and even stop it just as it stops in a black hole or at moving at the speed of light. And we do not have to travel the speed of light to slow time, or stop it.

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Time Dilation Clock Experiment.

- We all know about the effect of watches working in different speed if they are far from earth's gravity.
- the watch that is far from earth's gravity for example, watches in GPS satellite seems to be ticking faster than watches on earth.
- Now let's look at it in another way, where we introduce a factor in it while we experiment.
- Let us add a power source in it.
- So we take 2 watches that are identical.
- They consume the same power and move at the same rate when together.
- the power consumption of both the watch is that they consume 50% of battery charge in 12 hours.
- So now let us send one watch so far away that its clock is ticking twice as fast from the watch on earth.
- Meaning every one second on earth's watch, The watch in space ticks 2 seconds.
- Now after six hours on earth's watch let us compare the time and battery consumption.
- if we see that the space watch has ticked 12 hours then time dilation did happen.

- But now we should look at the battery too, the watch on Earth should consume 25% battery because it was running for six hours.
- And the watch in space should have consumed 50% because it was running for 12 hours.
- and if the battery was same of that of earth's battery which was 25%. Then the question arise where did the watch get its energy from?
- What really happened?
- Did the electrons in the battery in the watch in space move faster than that of earth. If yes then why?
- what does gravity do to matter for it to move slow?

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The Relationship Between Mass And Velocity On Space That Affects Time

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- It is seen that when light travels in space it is not experiencing time, the time for the Photon that travel in that speed has stopped.
- This is also said that nothing can travel the speed of light except light which means no one can experience stopped time.
- And the higher the mass the slower will be the speed in which it can travel.
- Electrons having more mass that a Photon will not reach the speed of light.
- Let me put this in a graph. In which I will have two axis 'x' and 'y', the x axis will show the speed of the object and the y axis will show the time the object experience.

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Diagram 2.1

In the diagram 2.1 let's understand the relation between time and speed (velocity in space)

- The y axis is the line of time experienced by things.
- The x axis is the speed of that thing.
- We can see that in x axis the point c is the speed of light which experience no time hence it creates a line on the x axis which is '0c'.
- Next we can take a point that is moving slower than c, and because it is moving slower than c it does not experience complete stop on time, but experience little time that I have shown in y axis as point 1. So it creates a line that is '1a'
- Now if this is a thing that speed alters your time experience, then at a point we can see in the graph that when there is no movement at all, does time experienced is the fastest
- In point j does time pass so fast that it ends in an instant

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- Now let's see any a new graph where instead of speed we will use mass.

mass of object
Diagram 2.2

- In the second diagram 2.2 we will see the relation between time and mass.
- The y axis is the line of time experienced by things, again.
- And the x axis is the mass of the things.
- In the x axis we can see the point b (this point represents the mass of black hole because it is the object that has seen to have the most mass and also researchers say that time slows or stops at the event horizon. In this graph let's assume time stops just as it stops at the speed of light.) The point is right on the x axis not experiencing time hence creating a line Ob.
- Next we can take a point that has less mass than point b, which is point c in this way we can see it is experiencing time at the point 1 on y axis.
- And so we go on till we come to the point h, which lets assume it is mass less. What happens to that object? Does it experience time the fastest just as the thing in diagram 2.1 that is not moving in space at all.

3 Let's connect the two diagrams.

- We see that the higher the velocity of things in space and the higher the mass of an object in space both experience no time at all, for them time stops.
- And the thing that is not moving at all and the object that has no mass experience time the fastest.

- The interesting question is this. What will happen if a heavy object with mass such as earth increase its velocity in space, more than the velocity at which it is moving now, does it's time slows? Because higher velocity does seems to slow time. If not then, why does it not slow time?

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Time / Mass / Velocity

- Now from the previous chapter if we see the things that happen, and if we accept the things that happen then, let's see what happens by using mass and speed both.
- We know that light travels at 299,792,458 m/s and time stops at that.
- Is there a number to which we can calculate the black holes mass. And according to that we can have a line of speed and a second line of mass.

Diagram 3-1

- Can we get an equation from this in which it shows us that any object with mass that travels at certain speed, it's time will stop.

- If yes we can find the earth's mass and the speed it need to travel, in which we can stop it's time.
- Black holes are said to be moving in , then what happens to it's time, because it's time is already at a stop, cause it's a black hole.
- Or is there no stop of time or time just keeps on slowing with increase in mass and speed.
- If the thing I have written are true the equation should have the mass of object, speed of object, which will show us the time of object.
- The equation $e=mc^2$ says that mass and energy are the same.
- If mass and energy is equal that means we can Equalize two objects of different mass, when the lesser mass objects velocity is increased.
- So the question is can we increase earth to a black hole, by increasing its velocity to high speed in space. If yes then at what velocity will have to accelerate earth too.
- I think energy as whole wants to be balanced and the things with more mass and on motion creates the same atmosphere in space for all matter in it.
- It looks like it restrict matter to move, react, or do anything.
- It makes it harder and harder for things to happen when there is more mass and velocity.

Ending notes.

I would like to thank you all for giving time to my hypothesis. I hope to learn more. If you find I am wrong anywhere please explain to me in simple language I can't understand equation.

Thank you

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